

**Impact of Glass Ceiling, Work Environment and Organizational Policy on Employee Performance:
Evidence from working women of Karachi.****Vineeka Pardeep Kumar¹**Research Scholar, Benazir School of Business – Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University Lyari, Karachi
Vineekasawlani99@Gmail.Com**Maham Batool²**Research Scholar, Benazir School of Business – Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University Lyari, Karachi
Mahambatool02@Gmail.Com**Mahnoor Khaliq³**Research Scholar, Benazir School of Business – Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University Lyari, Karachi
Mahnoorkhaliq7777@Gmail.Com**Waqas Bin Dilshad⁴**Assistant Professor, Benazir School of Business – Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University Lyari, Karachi
Link2waqas@Gmail.Com**ABSTRACT**

In the current era, we have seen that females are getting independent and entering the business world. Female workers are contributing to our society and working like males. Therefore, the motive of this study is to detect the factors affecting their work in different organizations in Karachi. Additionally, this attempt will help classify the causative factors that affect employee performance. The results of the study show three aspects responsible for employee performance which ultimately affects their performance and motivation level. The identified factors are Glass Ceiling, Organizational Policy, and Work Environment. After evaluating the information, it can be concluded that respondents come to an agreement regarding these factors affect their performance. According to the respondent's opinion in their organization glass ceiling exists and promotions in senior positions are not given on merit a basis. The respondents agreed that male employees hold influential positions in their organization and that affects their performance. The organizational policy and the work environment of their organization also demotivate them and become a factor in their performance. Therefore, this study identified three factors that affect employee performance and after collecting and analyzing the data it has proved that there is an impact of the glass ceiling, organizational policy, and work environment on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Glass Ceiling, Organization Policy, Work Environment, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Absence of women in top level management could be consider a universal problem as the quantity of females on higher designations observed lowest in maximum states. In 1999, the USA Division of Labor's defined the glass ceiling as an artificial blockage based on an attitudinal organizational prejudice that avoids capable persons especially women promoted to, management positions in entities (Catalyst, 1991). "Glass ceiling" is a terminology that define the unseen obstacles which become hurdle for females while getting top management positions (Pai and Vaidya 2009). Ceiling is known as the obstacle that stop the rising on development stage. On the other hand Glass replicates the hiddenness of the problem (Afza and Newaz 2008).

In past years, females are restricted to stay at home and they have to do home chores and maintained their homes. The female was only considered a wife and mother (AKOGLAN, 1997). In the last few years, the number of female workers is increasing in the workforce. But tis a common trend that female workers have littler career opportunities than male workers. There is a major reason for this problem for female workers is the concept of the GC. Glass Ceiling means unseen barriers that restrict the career opportunities for female workers. It is also explained by the situations in which the career progress of a potential person inside the group of people is restricted on same level because of discrimination, mostly racism This condition is recognized as the ceiling and here is a barrier upward and glass (transparent) because barrier is an unwritten and unofficial policy of an organization. Female workers have unequal career advancement and employment opportunities. (United Nations, 1995, P. 40). Female workers are incapable to get upward hierarchical positions in an organization. They are not included in economical policymaking (FWCW PARAS 152).

In our societies, male workers have achieved highest positions occupations as compared to female workers. In 1981, 'UN Convention on the Exclusion of all types of Discrimination in contradiction of Women came to reality in order to prevent inequality between females and males but still, female workers are facing inequalities in terms of seniority and promotions in jobs (AYTAC, 2001). These are the several effects of the GC on females workers. There are few followers claim about the glass ceiling GC) does not occur cause of the given factors:

- Women's rights and civil rights regulation that exists equality of Women.
- Job selections of woman stops from the managerial side.
- Women are highly qualified, for choosing prominent jobs.
- According to the conservative feminist group Independent Women's Forum, only 11% of corporate world boards included as a member

GLASS CLIFF

It is the latest symbol presented by the author (Ryan 2005) he demonstrates those issues females confront in higher-level roles in workplaces Ryan's research discoveries not only cover the private sector but also cover public sectors when women in higher administrative or managerial positions may face Glass cliff issues the study demonstrated sorts of agencies of federal as the author explains that in his studies (Newman 1994) there are threats that may fall off in cliff are company makes the policies that are not favorable for cliff personnel are not satisfied with their work-life balance and organization do injustice (Dolan 2004)the research result demonstrated that SES female personnel in distributive policy agencies usually have glass cliffs. To minimize this issue when organizations make favorable policies which will lead be if it's for both personnel and organization or females are influenced by decision-making for making policies (Ting Lee 2009).

Furthermore, the other researcher has also discovered the influence of organization culture and policies on worker performance & their output. Such as scholar (Hofstede 1980; Ouchi, 1981; and Bond, 1992; Magee, 2002) has said that Organization policies play a significant role in Org performance. However strong organizational policies support the development and employee performance, it also motivates employees towards achieving the organization goals and objectives. (Daft, 2010). Firms' performance also get improves if the employees are dedicated and organization policies are followed by well performed. (Mintzberg, 1987). In addition, working environment also impact the organization performance and this encourage on job effectiveness. A work environment is where the number of people work together and complete their given tasks at workplace. Increment in the level of job satisfaction shows greater value of employee's achievement. (Manthei, and Solmon, 2008).

However, effective human resource management in Org is an essential part of the firms in order to meet the anticipated outcomes and success (Genzorová, 2017). Another scholar (Bushiri, 2017) refers that behavior of workers get influenced by the organization work environment.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Studies have shown that female employees face discrimination issues among promotions to high positions jobs. These policies set by managers represent their organization's culture. As a result, the performance of female and minority employees is disrupted.

However, in the past few years, the ratio of female workers in organizations are increasing and females are competing with males but the organization's policy does not promote females on high-level jobs which are affecting their performance.

If this concept of GC is affecting the employee performance of foreign countries and other cities of Pakistan as well then, we must be known about the employee performance of Karachi.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- Does GC (glass ceiling) affect employee performance in Karachi?
- Does the work environment affect employee performance in Karachi?
- Does Organizational policy affect employee performance in Karachi?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE**GENERAL OBJECTIVE:**

The main goal is to examine the factors affecting on employee performances in Karachi.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE:

To investigate GC on worker's performance in Karachi.

To identify the effect of the Work environment on performance of employee in Karachi.

To explore the impact of Organizational policy on the female worker productivity Karachi.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

1. There is a significant relationship between glass ceiling and employee performance in SMEs of Karachi.
2. There is a significant relationship between work environment and employee performance in SMEs of Karachi.
3. There is a significant relationship between organizational policy and employee performance.

JUSTIFICATION:

There are many factors that are affecting and have a influential effect on worker's productivity in organization. Moreover, Glass ceiling can cause many problems which could affect the profitability of the organization and the lower ratio of GC leads to better organizational performance and help employees to perceive the organizational policies as fair.

Essentially, this study aims to evaluate the performance of female employees and minimize the effects of other

factors including GC in organizations. In addition, this study will be helpful for the researchers and scholars in their future studies and it will help them to broaden their knowledge.

LIMITATIONS

This particular study has certain limitations that need to be acknowledged. The restriction of this research is basically on primary data. The primary data takes longer time period in data collection information like sources including surveys, questionnaires, etc., and putting the data into excel, analyzing the data, and then finding conclusion also takes time so it may affect the outcomes.

Data has been collected through a minimum sample size of 300 samples due to limited time and this may diminish the general factors of the answers. In addition, for conducting research we will mainly focus on the Organizations of Karachi and data collected from female employees.

SCOPE

Our study focused on how the GC ceiling, work environment, and organization policy, influenced employee performance in organizations in Karachi. Outcomes of the study showed that the ratio of female workers is increasing day by day in the corporate sector with this the opportunity barriers are also creating hurdles for them and one of the main barriers is the G. Ceiling.

Therefore, this study aims to examine the drawbacks and solutions caused by the GC. The study is going to be conducted in Karachi's organizations (including all SMEs in Karachi).

ASSUMPTION

There are many factors that effects on EP but among all variables GC plays a major role in Employee Performance of firm in Pakistan. IVs of our study also have a dependency on other variables such as Organization Policy is dependent on strategic leaders or Managers, and Work Environment is dependent on employees and managers.

LITERATURE REVIEW**THEORETICAL REVIEW:**

This chapter involves the earlier theories which are related to our study. In this chapter, we analyzed the different research theories and evaluate the glass ceiling and other factors effects on employee performance.

EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AND GLASS CEILING

Khuong and Chi, (2017) conducted this study in Pakistan and collected the data from Lahore and suggested that the unfair behavior in the workplace which is created between males and females in the organizations is known as the "Glass Ceiling". It has been suggested that those corporates that have a higher level of GC effects negatively to the productivity of the organizations on the other hand the lower level of GC lead to a higher commitment of female employees which effects positively the performance of corporate sectors. According to Jawahar and Hemmasi (2006), organizations should give proper attention and equal career advancement to female employees to defend the organization. If the firm' implements facilities for females and provides opportunities to women employees.

Arulampalam Et Al. (2007) has found that all the public and private sector organizations are facing the Glass ceiling issues. There is also discrimination in wages which was analyzed by the researcher. Further, the difference in pay gap depends upon the public and private sectors, the gap is high in the top-level positions and it is low in the lower-level positions and that is known as the "Sticky Floor" effect.

According to Leutwiler & Kleiner (2003), stereotypical thinking still exists among women. It is regarding job placement, hiring, promotion, rewards, and raises. If women do not get the desirable promotion on a timely basis so this could lead to a decline in organizational productivity. On the other hand, if the organization shows concern for their female employees so this could improve employee performance and it will also impact positively on the organization's performance.

The researcher has also observed that many other factors are obstacles to women's promotion decisions moreover the perception of manager such as conflicts of professional and personal life. He evaluated the gender biases challenged by females all over the world. Even in many developed countries, many hurdles are faced by women for surviving in their job. (Mohamed Zainal, 2009).

Moreover, the researcher has also evaluated that employee commitment and GC are interlinked with each other. This researcher has surveyed different regions of Pakistan and suggested that female employees are restricted to be promoted to the higher level of the organization hierarchy which has decreased the satisfaction of women employees and directly affects the performance of the organization. (Wright 1989, 1997).

EMPLOYEES PERFORMANCE AND WORK ENVIRONMENT:

An employee' fitness and unfitness at a workplace depends on the work environment. Certain factors of the bodily work environment are essential to be reformed, for instance, the lighting, office arrangement, furniture, and floor Brill. (Mccoy and Evans 2005).

A workplace which has improved work environment can help employees to improve their performance by 5 to 10% (Brill, 1992). On the other hand, a few elements of the work environment can cause a disturbance in female employees. These factors are the design or arrangement of the office and the lighting of the office (Boyce Et Al., 2003). If an employee gets stressed at the workplace, then the performance of their job will decrease and becomes

a troubling factor for the organization (McCoy and Evans, 2005).

Further, Khawar Nadeem and Aqeel Ahmad conducted this study in the region of Lahore Pakistan and evaluated the effect of the work environment on employee performance, data was collected by distributing questionnaires to individual managers and the findings of the study have shown that the physical work environment is moderately present in the employees. The sphere is changing rapidly and employees' hopes and fulfillment are also varying according to that.

The culture of an organization modifies over time to survive with such active variations and encounter the varying demand of employee's hopes and fulfillment. Therefore, helpful beliefs by Ritchie are measured a motivational tool that supports employee's performance effectively and confirms better output (Ritchie, 2000).

(Mohammad Jasim Uddin¹, Saad Md. Maroof Hossain) conducted this study in Bangladesh in 2012, qualitative approach was used to carry out the study in which comprehensive interviews were directed at GP, which is the biggest cellular operator with more than 32 million subscribers in Bangladesh. This enterprise is a joint venture between Telenor (55.8%) and Grameen Telecom operation (34.2%). The interviews were carried out in Grameenphone. Applicants encompassed most senior level, mid-level and operational-level employees moreover HR department, the paper is used in interviews in other relevant sectors such as marketing, regulation affair, corporate affairs, government, and strategic relations, business and societal relations, strategy, and planning. In conclusion, this study revealed that several characteristics of organizational culture have a significant positive effect on the performance of the firm. The study drawn out diverse cultural traits of organizations.

FACTORS OF WORK ENVIRONMENT THAT AFFECTS THE EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

A smart and compassionate work environment empowers employees to perform effectively, creating their understanding, skills, and competencies in a best manner and provide high-quality organizational service in a limited available resource. Based on this research the factors are supervisor support, job benefits, physical work environment, and feedback on performance.

Supervisor Support: A supervisor is also acknowledged as an individual who has experienced leadership qualities, an individual who can solve problems, and also a role model for the low-level of organizational management (Adair, 1988; Nijman, 2004). It is necessary for the supervisor to play their role which is to constrain to the association. If full assurance is given, it will lead to affirmative results in the employee performance (Blau, 1964).

JOB BENEFITS: Rossett and Gautier (1991) indicated the objective of a job benefit is to guide to strengthen the performance of employees. Job benefits also support the performance of employees. **Bodily Work Environment:** A bodily work environment can effect in a person fitting or misfitting level with the environment at the workplace. A bodily work environment is as well characterized as an ergonomic workplace. McCoy and Evans (2005) have identified that the features of the work environment want to be appropriate therefore, the employees would not be stressed while performing their job. In their research, they also quoted that the physical features play an important role in building relationships in the workplace. The results of performance of employees can be enlarged from 5% to 10% dependent on the development of the bodily workplace plan at their workplace (Brill, 1992).

This study was conducted by Christabella P. Bushiri at Drae Salam Region, this particular study discovered that the organization's work environment has great effect on employees as far as defendants are concerned. The study establish that it is important for organization to improve its bodily work environment to influence employees to be with the organization, work comfortably and perform their job. Hellriegel & Slocum (2009) said in their study, organizational culture can improve employee performance on a large scale if it is understood to them what sustains a culture. A durable organizational culture cares the alteration and builds the performance of employees by motivating them toward their objective. Lastly modeling and guiding the behavior of employees in a specific direction should be at the upper of operational and functional strategies (Daft, 2010). The writers of this study are Mohammad Jasim Uddin¹, Rumana Huq Luva² & Saad Md. Maroof Hossain has evaluated that the culture of an organization has a significant effect on the performance of the organization. This article has drawn different cultural traits of organizations as well as shown the vital connection between culture and performance. This qualitative research assisted the paper with its forceful and comprehensive explanations.

EMPLOYEES PERFORMANCE AND WORK ENVIRONMENT

Organizations are deliberated as a structure devising embedded parts that need to be organized for developing policy efficiently and effectively. The combined quantities of the organizational policy control the methods by which policy is developed, applied, followed, and evaluated. Organizations are giving enormous opportunities and challenges to policymakers. The policies of the policymakers become the organization's culture. In addition, management must involve Work-life policies are the most important to achieve the effectiveness of the organization. Cause employees in decision-making to prevent conflict between the management and employees. (Zainuddin 2018).

This study was conducted by Zainuddin in 2018 in Kenya with a sample size of 30 along with a descriptive research technique, further study findings indicate that the policies for promotions have a straight and distant impact on the performance of any organization. In addition, it also concludes that employee well-being policies considerably impact the performance of banks in Kenya.

Further, HR policies can also influence positively and negatively the motivation of the employees. A satisfied employee with the organization’s human resource practices will be attached and motivated enough to accomplish organization’s objectives. (Danish, R.Q, & Usman, A., 2010).

The study was conducted by Amir Ali Khushk in Hyderabad. The article highlights the HR policies and practices and their influence on the performance and satisfaction of employees with questionnaires results identified which concluded that practical HR policies not only motivates the current employees but also attracts new talent for the organization, retains the old one, and encourage the workforce in their organizational commitment.

As we know that the world is growing so fast and the increased demand of expectation and satisfaction of the employees also transform according to the changing environment. Organizational policies also adapt to such dynamic changes and try to fulfill the increased demand of expectations and satisfaction of employees.

Therefore, a compassionate policy toward employees is measured as a motivational tool that enhances the performance and productivity of employees (Ritchie, 2000).

However, an employee performs well and smoothly and ensures better productivity if the organizational policies are in support of employees. These organizational policies led to successful organizations. Researchers argue that organizational culture or policies cannot be imitative so that it will become a reason of organization’s sustainability. Barney’s research on the Resource-based view argues that sustainability of an organization depends on the standards, uncommonness, and sustainability of the policies (Barney, 1986 and 1991).

According to researchers, Performance means the ability to implement exact task in exact manner that can be dignified as extraordinary, normal, or little on the scale. There are two extents of performance; one is the action dimension (which means the behavioral trait) and the second is the outcome dimension (which means the performance trait) (Roe, 1999; Campbell, McCloy, Oppler, and Sager, 1993; Kanfer, 1990).

Moreover, articles have researched that here is a connection between Organizational Policy and Employee Performance. Magee explained that organization’s policy is naturally related to organization’s practices (Magee, 2002). Organizational Policy enhances the employee’s performance on a large scale if it can be communicated to its employees (Hellriegel and Slocum, 2009). These researchers have argued that the policy of an organization permits their employees to be familiar with the previous and latest procedures of job and guides them about future organizational goals.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK:

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

A research design is a simple design specifying the method and process for collecting the data and analyzing the information relevant for the research project.

Saunders Et Al (2007) explored that there are two type of research qualitative and quantitative, these two types are different in terms of numeric or non-numeric forms. For conducting this study, the Quantitative Method for collecting the data will be used, data collection will be by both means primary and secondary, Secondary data will be gathered from existing female employees of the targeted firms, whereas primary data will also be collected by interviewing and survey method from the population of this particular study means from minorities and female employees.

PROCEDURE

The cause of data that we practice for gathering the facts for our study is primary. The primary data is gathered directly from the defendants of the study. Data is based on factors affecting employee performance and it is obtained from the different organizations in Karachi.

A designed Questionnaire is adapted from the research articles to gather the information from the employees. We circulated the questionnaire to different organizations.

Furthermore, surveys and interviews are also taken with the employees for reliable data analysis. That particular questionnaire is structured, close handed as it will elaborate the correlations among the DV and IVs variables. The study is mainly focusing on quantitative analysis techniques. The information collected from the employees to analyze those factors and further the data is used to interpret the results. After further collecting the data, it is enclosed, processed, and analyzed through SPSS.

POPULATION

The population for this specific study will be female employees and minorities because GC refer to decreasing the career advancements of female employees therefore, the obvious and accurate population for this study will be females. Besides, the population will be from the SMEs of Karachi, which means existing employees of the corporations of Karachi.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING METHODS

This study is based on a quantitative research method. The sample size of this study is 200 female workers of SMEs. In his study, the data will be collected through Convenience Sampling Method, non-probability samples.

INSTRUMENTAL SELECTION

In this study, we will collect our data through the adopted questionnaire. A total of 200 questionnaires will be distributed to collect data through the primary source. The questionnaire will be based on a Likert scale.

VARIABLES:

This research is founded on dependent and independent variables. We have four independent variables that are GC, WE, and OP and the dependent variable of our research is the employee work performance.

VARIABLES	TYPES
Glass Ceiling	Independent Variable
Work Environment	Independent Variable
Organizational Policy	Independent Variable
Employee Performance	Dependent Variable

STUDY MODEL

To established the relationship between other factors that are affecting employee performance. The multiple regression equation of this study is;

▪ **MATHEMATICAL MODEL**

$Y = F (X^1, X^2, X^3 \dots \dots \dots)$

$EP = F (GC, WE, OP)$

▪ **STATISTICAL MODEL**

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X^1 + \beta_2X^2 + \beta_3X^3 + \beta_4X^4 + \mu$$

$$EP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (GC) + \beta_2 (WE) + \beta_3 (OP) + \mu$$

Y is Dependent variable of Employee performance (EP)

B0 is regression constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2,$ and β_3 are coefficients of independent variables

X1 = glass ceiling (GC)

X2 = work environment (WE)

X3 = organization policy (OP)

μ = error term

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

In this part, we analyzed the data and interpret the findings of our data and give a conclusion on the Factors affecting Employee Performance in Karachi. Firstly, we conducted a survey through questionnaires and put the collected data on excel then we run it on SPSS software to analyze the data and the results and findings are displayed in form of tables, pie charts, and diagrams. This part includes findings from data, correlation output, regression output, and a summary of the findings.

ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION:

The population of our research was 200, who are female employees of any organization in Karachi. We have gathered data from different organizations, banks, schools, etc. Plaintiffs' complete questionnaires related to their backgrounds like age and the period of time they served in their current organization.

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION:

The respondent's gender of our study is female with a 100% ratio of female workers. In this study, the information has been gathered from female participants.

4.2.2 AGE OF RESPONDENTS

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
18 -24	119	59.5
25-31	56	28
32-38	12	6
39-45	7	3.5
Over 45years	6	3
Grand Total	200	100

This table indicates the age of the respondents of our research. It has discovered that 59.5% of the respondents' age is between 18-24 years, 28% of the respondent's age is between 25-31 years, 6% of the respondents age is between 32-38 years, 3.5% of respondent's age is between 39-45 years, and 3% of the respondents' age is over 45 years.

PERIOD OF TIME SERVED IN THE CURRENT ORGANIZATION:

This table indicates the period of time they served in the present organization of the respondents of our research. It has been discovered that 54.1% of the respondents stated less than 1 year, 25.5% of the respondents stated 1 to 3 years' experience, 9.2% of the respondents stated 4 to 6 years' experience, 5.1 % of the respondents stated 7 to 10 years' experience, and lastly 6.1% of the respondents stated that they have served in the present organization more than 10 years. It means that most of the data was gathered from those employees who served the organization for less than 1 year in their present organizations.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS:

In this research, the SPSS software was used and calculated the extent of multiple regression and discover the output of descriptive statistics, reliability statistics, regression model summary, ANOVA, and Coefficient.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS:

descriptive statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
EP	4.0463	.31907	200
GC	4.072	.4559	200
OP	4.0670	.26846	200
WE	4.0538	.30374	200

The descriptive data for the study are displayed in this table. It says that 200 questionnaires made up the Sample size, and that the mean is calculated as the total of all values divided by the sample size. The standard deviation value represents how near the data is to the mean value. The data is closer to the mean value, which is desirable, if the standard deviation number is close to zero.

The average employee performance score is 4.0463, and the standard deviation is 0.31907; the average grade point average (GC) score is 4.072, and the standard deviation is 0.4559; the average organizational policy rating is 4.0670, and the SD is 0.26846; and the average work environment score is 4.0538. Overall, results conclude that the standard deviation values of all variables are nearby 0 which indicates that the figures are close to the mean value.

CORRELATION

Correlations					
		EP	GC	OP	WE
Pearson Correlation	EP	1.000	.684	.847	.856
	GC	.684	1.000	.271	.193
	OP	.847	.271	1.000	.917
	WE	.856	.193	.917	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	EP	.	.020	.000	.000
	GC	.020	.	.000	.012
	OP	.000	.000	.	.000
N	WE	.000	.012	.000	.
	EP	200	200	200	200
	GC	200	200	200	200
	OP	200	200	200	200
	WE	200	200	200	200

This table displays the relation between DV and I. Variables. In research study, we have identified, results which are revealed in the table and results indicate that GC is positively correlated to the EP (.684), OP is positively correlated to the EP (0.847), and WE is also positively correlated to the EP(0.856).

The overall results show that all independent variables are positively correlated to the Dependent variable which is EP . If any of the independent variables rise then the dependent variable will also rise and vice versa.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS:

model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	theDurbin-Watson
1	.870 ^a	.757	.753	.15848	2.135

a. Predictors: (Constant), WE, GC, OP

b. Dependent Variable: EP

The model's executive summary is included in the table. The correlation coefficient, or R, describes how the independent and dependent factors are correlated to one another. Because it is so near to 1, the value of R, which is 0.870, indicates a significant positive link between the dependent and independent variables.

R², a statistical term that indicates the coefficient of determination, determines whether or not a model fits the data. Performance of employees is the variable y and variable X's have a variance of 75.7%, which is the value of R² (Glass ceiling, ORG. policy, and work environment). R² determines how much of a dependent variable's variation that can be related to a change in an independent variable. The results demonstrate that the EP has changed by 75.7%.

Based on the rule of thumb, the Durbin-Watson value must be in a range of 1.5-2.5 because it indicates no auto correlation. The DW = 2.135 so it clarify that it does not have any autocorrelation exists in the model summary.

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (ANOVA):

Anova

Model	sum of squares	DF	Mean Square	F	sig
regression	15.337	3	5.112	203.544	.000 ^b
residual	4.923	197	.025		
total	20.260	200			

a. Dependent Variable: EP

b. Predictors: (Constant), WE, GC, OP

In regression ANOVA indicates all fitness shown in the model. The rule of thumb (ROT), declares the Significance Value must be low than (0.05) and the F value should be greater than 3.14. In study the significance is 0.00 & the F is 203.544 this is also more than 3.14 and this indicates that fitness of model. Further, the Degree of Freedom value calculates estimates and tells the total independent variables in the study. In our study,

the value of DF is 3, which shows 3 independent variables in the study and there are 200 total samples with a residual of 197.

REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS

MODEL		UNSTANDARDIZED COEFFICIENTS		STANDARDIZED T	SIG.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	Constant	-.075	.227	-.330	.742
	GC	.020	.026	.029	0.04
	OP	.482	.108	.406	.000
	WE	.513	.094	.488	.000

DV: EP

The table is showing the regression Coefficient. Value of each IV’s (GC, OP, and WE) shows the effect on the dependent variable (EP) and their significance. The rule of thumb is that the T statistic value should be greater than 2 and the value of significance should be less than 0.05. In our study, the BETA value of the glass ceiling is 0.20 this Indicates GC positive impression on EP, a unit increase in GC leads to an increase in the EP by 0.20. Furthermore, between GC, EP there is a significant correlation cause the significance value is 0.04 and its P < 0.05 and the t value is 2.778 which is T>2.

The beta value of an organizational policy is 0.482, indicating that the OP has a positive effect on EP; a unit increase in OP relates to a 0.482 rise in EP. Because the p values is 0.00, which is less than 0.05, and the T value is 4.467, which is larger than 2, there is a strong connection between OP and EP.

Workplace environment's beta value is 0.513, indicating that the WE have a positive influence on EP; a unit rise in EP leads to a 0.513 increase in EP. There is a significant link between WE and EP since the value of significance is 0.00, which is less than 0.05, and the T value is 5.466, which exceeds than 0. Overall findings of table indicating all the IV’s are strongly influencing of the DV and each variable is showing significance in the above table.

MODEL EQUATION

In this research MR (multi regression) was conducted to check the influence among all these variables.

The multiple regression model equation is,

Employee Performance= (-0.75) + (0.020) glass ceiling + (0.482) organizational policy + (0.513) work environment.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X^1 + \beta_2 X^2 + \beta_3 X^3 + \beta_4 X^4 + \mu$$

$$EP = - 0.75 + 0.020 (GC) + 0.482 (OP) + 0.513 (WE) + \mu$$

FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

After collection of data, conclusions, recommendations and the findings of research are summarized. This research has analyzed the Factors affecting Employees Performance (in Karachi). The study determined how the glass ceiling, organizational policy, and work environment affect employee performance.

CONCLUDING THE FINDINGS

This research, practically observed relationship among (DV and IV’s) variables. It is quantitative research and determined the impact of (GC, OP, and WE) on EP (DV).

We also conducted survey by the help of questionnaires filled by female employees within different organizations of Karachi with a sample size of 200 and asked how these independent variables impact on employee performance. The study revealed that GC, OP, and WE are affecting employee performance. The study found that if these factors are in favor of female employees, then it will lead to better performance of female employees. If the organizational policy supports their employees and the work environment is satisfied then the performance of female employees will grow. If the glass ceiling will decrease and equal opportunity will be given on a merit basis so there is a high chance of better performance of female employees and that will lead to a success of an organization.

CONCLUSION

This study has attempted to inspect the factors affecting performance of female employees in different organizations of Karachi. It is anticipated that this research findings provided by the present study will be helpful to policymakers in different organizations of Karachi. While widespread researches have been completed on female employees in different countries and cities on different topics but only few of studies has been done to inspect the glass ceiling effects in Karachi. This area is unmapped in the arena of management studies in Karachi. This research has recognized few factors which are influencing employee performance and the reasons for glass ceilings in organizations. The outcomes of this study would serve as a foundation for further studies of employee

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performance in Karachi. This research will help in facilitating organizations to reform their total policies, work environment, and structure. The development and employment of females, which has become necessary portion of our society nowadays. It has become important for organizations to move ahead of their competitors by increasing their growth. However, factors like a glass ceiling, organizational policy, and work environment affect employee performance. Females which are not getting expected and deserved promotions, they have lesser amount of motivation. Having lesser amount of motivation leads some female employees to decrease their performance which will also affect the whole organization's performance. On the other hand, motivated female employees lead to an increase in their job performance. It is very necessary for organizations to make favorable policies and better work environments for employees. It is observable that the achievement and confidence of female employees will rise if they are satisfied with the organizational policies and work environment. Thus, a female will start working happier and more motivated. If female employees sense worthy emotionally, improved performance can be achieved. Conversely, the presence of discrimination, an ill-mannered environment, impolite attitudes, and a traumatic and impatient environment are the reasons that decline motivation and also disturb their performance and mental health. If female employees are valued as an outcome of their achievements and get promotions, the organization will accomplish its objectives quicker because their employees are motivated and work hard for the success of the organization.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Organizations should make policies that are equal for all employees and are in favor of employees. Organizations should provide a better work environment to employees. Organizations should provide equal career opportunities to female employees and they should involve female employees in decision-making and promote them to senior-level positions. Females are also an asset to our country so organizations should treat them equally and give them equal rights.

AREA OF FURTHER RESEARCH

This research has only rigorous on the noticeable organizations from diverse sectors which are located in Karachi. The sample size was also limited due to the shortage of time. Therefore, the research can be conducted in a specific sector or in another city with an increased sample size. Further, the study can be managed on this matter by captivating into concern all the limitations of our study.

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